

Editorial

The problems of present-day society are usually complex and solutions to these problems may be achieved through interdisciplinary approach. Differential Equations have been extensively employed to model real world applications that exhibit continuous dynamics. This modeling effort is on the rise due to the necessity created in the understanding of the complex phenomena inherently present in these problems. This makes the study of such problems more challenging and rewarding.

Of late scientists are deeply engaged in studying problems involving societal concerns. In the past, important contributions to understand the real-world problems around us have been made in various domains, such as social sciences, finance, environment, human behavior, strategic decision-making, information and knowledge management, public policy, highway transportation networks, telecommunication networks, immunological health care systems, computational systems, electrical and mechanical structures. In recent years, nonlinear dynamics and chaos have started attracting a great deal of attention, and many useful results have been documented in the literature.

Now a days, dynamical system studies are applied by policymakers, academicians, educators, and managers in many areas of natural sciences, social sciences, engineering, and technology. The reconstruction of system structure from data in complex system science is a challenging task and robust methodologies needed to be developed to handle such complex systems in view of their vast application potential. Much of the developments in modern science and technology has been attributed to our understanding of the nonlinear phenomena. Mathematical analysis of nonlinear systems has rendered unification of a variety of problems in diverse areas. It is in this world that infinitesimal inputs may result in macroscopic outputs or vice versa.

It is the endeavour of the Editorial Team of the Journal of Innovation Sciences and Sustainable Technologies to bring out the investigations connected with these nonlinear explorations in a series of special issues with the series title being “Real World Dynamical Systems and Numerics”. Numerics in these studies have a significant influence in building effective and more accurate models.

This issue is the first in this series organized by Drs. Flank David Bezerra, Jocirei Dias Ferreira and Severino Horácio da Silva of Brazil as Guest Editors.

The Guest Editors have selected the articles published in Part-1 of this special issue upon a thorough review process. These papers are embodiment of recent advances in neural fields, cosmology and the disease cancer. The studies propose models based on differential equations on finite and infinite dimensional Banach spaces.

Series Editors

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